

boxyl stretching region¹⁶ it frustrated attempts to demonstrate whether carboxyl group is free or not. Attempts to protonate COO^- by HCl to produce $[\text{Co}(\text{hist H})(\text{BigH})_2]^{3+}$ led to decomposition of the complex.

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Ionic Activity Products of $\text{AlPO}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and $\text{FePO}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ in Acid Soils. Part II. Consecutive Leachings of Soils with and without Adding Phosphate in Neutral Salt Solutions

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THE constancy of pK_{sp} values of $\text{FePO}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ & $\text{AlPO}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ has been reported before on acid soils treated with KCL, $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4$, and CaCl_2 solutions of ionic strengths 0.02 and 0.04, the extractions being done on soils which were not P-treated. In the present paper three soils have been chosen in

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the pH range 4 to 6 extracted four times consecutively with 0.02M KCl (a) with out P-treatment and (b) with P-treatment, using prepared AIP, FeP and a mixture of (AIP+FeP). The phosphates were prepared according to the method of Gasser and Bloomfield², and had the compositions :

Aluminium Phosphate : $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3 : \text{P}_2\text{O}_5$ Compound formed.
= 1 : 1.9 $\text{Al}(\text{OH})(\text{H}_2\text{PO}_4)_2$

Iron phosphate : $\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_3 : \text{P}_2\text{O}_5$ Compound formed is a mixture of $\text{Fe}(\text{OH})(\text{H}_2\text{PO}_4)_2$ and $\text{Fe}(\text{H}_2\text{PO}_4)_3$
= 1 : 2.5

Details about the soil samples used are given in Table 1. Soils C-1 and C-2 were from Cinchona plantation and J-1 from wheat Cultivation.

TABLE I

Soil no.	pH.	Locality	Family	Depth of Sampling.	Colour	Total P Content	Organic Carbon
C-1	4.70	Mun-song	Hilly forest soil	0"-9"	Brownish black	7/100 29,700	1.43
C-2	5.77	Labdh	"	"	"	10,000	1.60
J-1	5.90	Jabal-pore	Sandy	"	Yellowish brown	12,500	0.28

Each soil was subjected to the following treatment.

- 1.0 g of soil + 500 ml of 0.02 M KCl solution
- 5.0 " " + 500 " " " " " "
- 5.0 " " + 0.5 g Fep. + 500 ml of 0.02 M KCl solution
- 5.0 " " + 0.5 " AIP + " " " "
- 5.0 " " + (0.25 " AIP + 0.25 " Fep) + " "

So that there were altogether 15 sets for the three soils. The mixtures were taken in separate bottles into which 1 ml of chloroform was added to prevent fungus growth. The bottles were shaken end-to-end for 2-3 hr a day during 10 days. At the completion of this period the pH of the soil suspension was measured using a Cambridge pH meter, and iron, aluminium and phosphate contents were determined in the filtrates.

After completion of the first extract 500 ml. of fresh 0.02M KCL was added to each bottle, any soil adhering to the filter paper being washed back to this bottle with the solution. This procedure was repeated four times with all the soils allowing equilibrium to attain each time. The pK_{sp} values of $\text{FePO}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and $\text{AlPO}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ were computed on each leaching according to the procedure described in the earlier paper. Ref of this Journal the results are shown in Table 2.

Results and Discussions

(i) *Change in pH* : values of soil suspensions were greatly influenced by the soil : solution ratio, an increase in the ratio from 1.0 g. to 5.0 g. soil leading to a lowering of pH in each case. This effect was more pronounced in the Cinchona soils (C-1, C-2) but less

TABLE 2—pK_{sp} VALUES OF IRON AND ALUMINIUM PHOSPHATE IN CONSECUTIVE LEACHINGS

Soil. No.	Wt./g.	1st extraction.		2nd extraction.		3rd extraction.		4th extraction.		Treatment
		pH	pK _{sp} FePO ₄ 2H ₂ O							
C-1	1.0	4.40	32.63	4.86	32.96	5.06	33.00	5.16	32.71	29.25
	5.0	4.04	32.46	4.17	32.49	4.44	33.12	4.32	33.55	31.17
	5.0	4.16	30.75	4.04	31.47	4.26	31.74	4.62	31.62	28.73
	5.0	4.09	30.43	4.12	32.49	4.40	32.81	4.74	32.68	30.14
	5.0	4.12	31.06	4.15	31.60	4.39	31.86	4.60	31.70	28.97
C-2	1.0	5.40	32.34	5.46	32.71	5.64	32.49	6.10	31.69	28.10
	5.0	5.13	32.05	5.46	32.41	5.65	31.87	5.61	32.56	29.65
	5.0	4.77	30.77	4.62	31.75	4.80	33.75	5.02	32.92	29.95
	5.0	5.00	30.68	4.84	31.32	5.15	32.68	5.28	31.76	28.22
	5.0	4.95	30.85	4.68	31.39	4.99	32.31	5.12	31.84	28.24
J-1	1.0	6.38	31.74	6.20	32.35	5.54	33.92	5.72	33.31	31.85
	5.0	6.27	30.44	6.32	31.39	6.00	33.17	5.95	33.00	29.47
	5.0	5.68	29.44	5.70	30.06	5.70	30.66	5.62	30.88	27.45
	5.0	6.06	29.34	5.96	29.83	5.82	31.14	5.69	31.83	28.08
	5.0	5.80	29.64	5.76	29.86	5.70	30.23	5.60	31.17	27.76

Here, o=no. phosphate, F=iron phosphate, A=aluminium phosphate and F+A=iron and aluminium phosphate

NOTES

marked in the Jabalpure soil. The pH values of soils increased linearly with successive leaching. The increase of pH was evidently due to the gradual replacement of hydrogen ions from the system by potassium ions.

The phosphate-treated samples showed greater lowering of pH than the untreated samples. This was probably due to fact that the phosphates used were originally acidic (Vide analytical report).

(ii) *Ionic products* : The pK_{sp} values of $FePO_4 \cdot 2H_2O$ showed somewhat higher values in the system containing 1.0 g. soil than that containing 5.0 g (Table 2) showing the influence of soil : solution ratio.

It is a point of interest that the pK_{sp} values mostly showed a gradual increase with pH which occurs with consecutive leachings but tends to fall after the third leachings.

The phosphate treated soils provided lower pK_{sp} values than the untreated soil samples in all the cases (Table 2)

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